

UPDATED DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (year 3)

Deliverable 1.6

Updated data management plan (year 3)

HIGH HORIZONS – D1.6

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Version 1.2	Corrections and updates made on version 1.1 (17 June 2024)
Version 1.3	New structure added to the document to reflect intermediate reporting towards a final DMP (18 July 2024)
Version 2.0	Internally revised and approved version (28 August 2024)
Version 2.1	Updated draft of version 2.0 (30 June 2025)
Version 3.0	Internally revised and approved version (22 August 2025)

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition/Description
AKHS	Aga Khan Health Services (Kenya)
BELNET	Belgian National Research & Education Network
CARBOMICA	Resource optimisation tool for CARBOn Mitigation Interventions in healthCare facilities
CeSHHAR	Centre for Sexual Health and HIV/AIDS Research (Zimbabwe)
DG	Data generation
DMP	Data management plan
DOI	Digital object identifier
DR	Data reuse
EWS	Early warning system
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable (data)
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KI	Karolinska Institutet (Sweden)
LSHTM	London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine (United Kingdom)
MNCH	Maternal, Neonatal, and Child Health
POPIA	Protection of Personal Information Act (South Africa)
RDM	Research data management
TNO	Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research (The Netherlands)
UGent	Ghent University (Belgium)
UGRAZ	University of Graz (Austria)
UK	United Kingdom
UKRI	UK Research and Innovation
ULUND	Lund University (Sweden)
UTH	University of Thessaly (Greece)
WHO	World Health Organisation
Wits RHI	Research institute of the University of the Witwatersrand (South Africa)
WOMBAT	Work Observation Method by Activity Timing
WP	Work Package

1 Background

1.1 Data management plan updates

HIGH Horizons is committed to apply the Open Science principles, both in the context of scholarly publishing, i.e. open access to publications and open peer review, and research data management (RDM), i.e. the generation of findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR) data.

At the start of the HIGH Horizons project, we wrote a publication policy¹ and a Data Management Plan. The publication policy of November 2022, also project deliverable D1.3, confirms the Open Access principles and was expanded with standard operating procedures and the establishment of a rotating Publication Committee in September 2024.

The first Data Management Plan (DMP) was initially written in [DMPonline](#), an online tool that guides its users through the DMP template of the funding agency and that is hosted at BELNET which holds/stores the data management plans on behalf of the client (i.e. Ghent University) on secure servers in Belgium. The resulting online DMP was downloaded as a Word document and submitted as project deliverable D1.4 in November 2022 (1). The first update of the HIGH Horizons DMP in August 2024², project deliverable D1.5, was based on the original version, but was restructured to reflect intermediate reporting towards a final data management 'plan' (2, 3). This second update, deliverable D1.6, builds further on the 2024 DMP (4).

1.2 Data management procedures

With Ghent University coordinating the HIGH Horizons project, the consortium partners apply the Ghent University's policy framework on Research Data Management (5) as good as possible. While our European partners are familiar with the EU's policy on Open Science, our African partners (i.e. Aga Khan Health Services in Kenya, Wits Health

¹ [Project deliverable D1.3](#) is available on the [CORDIS website](#).

² Approval of project deliverable D1.5 is pending and expected before end of 2025.

Consortium in South Africa and CeSHHAR in Zimbabwe) need to comply as well with national procedures for data protection and management, including the Data Protection Act 2019 of Kenya (6), the Protection of Personal Information Act (POPIA) of South Africa (7), and the Data Protection Act 2021 of Zimbabwe (8).

The World Health Organisation (WHO), another HIGH Horizons partner, complies with its personal data protection framework, which includes the WHO Personal Data Protection Policy and the UN Personal Data Protection and Privacy Principles (9).

1.3 Data management support

For the HIGH Horizons data management plan, the consortium is supported by the research data management team at Ghent University and by partner leads and data stewards from consortium partners for additional (country-specific) guidance.

In August 2025, the following persons are supporting and responsible for the HIGH Horizons research data management:

- In Belgium:
 - Scientific coordinator: Stanley Luchters³ – Ghent University & CeSHHAR
 - Project manager (including RDM): Birgit Kerstens – Ghent University (UGent)
- In Austria:
 - Partner lead: Ilona Otto – University of Graz (UGRAZ)
 - Data managers & researchers: Tobias Monthaler & Katharina Wieser – University of Graz
- In Denmark:
 - Project lead & data manager: Jørn Toftum – Technical University of Denmark (Technical University of Denmark)
- In Greece:
 - Project lead: Barbara Mouchtouri – University of Thessaly (UTH)
 - Data managers & researchers: Michalis Koureas & Evangelos Kokkalis – University of Thessaly

³ The HIGH Horizons scientific coordinator is also one of the two internal ethics advisors of the project.

- In Sweden:
 - Partner lead & data manager (primarily for data related to the testing and evaluation of the early warning system app): Chuansi Gao – Lund University (ULUND)
 - Partner lead & data manager (primarily for Swedish pregnancy register data and data generated in HIGH Horizons studies such as the health worker assessment and the early warning system message development): Olof Stephansson – Karolinska Institutet (KI)
- In the United Kingdom:
 - Deputy project coordinator & partner lead: Debra Jackson – London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine (LSHTM)
 - Data manager: Nasser Fardousi – London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine
- In Kenya:
 - Partner lead: Sohail Baloch – Aga Khan Health Services (AKHS), Kenya
 - Data manager: James Siku – Aga Khan Health Services, Kenya
- In South Africa:
 - Partner lead: Shobna Sawry – Wits RHI
 - Data manager: Jean Le Roux – Wits RHI
- In Zimbabwe:
 - Partner lead: Fortunate Machingura – CeSHHAR
 - Data manager: Jeffrey Dirawo – CeSHHAR

1.4 Data utility

The HIGH Horizons project addresses key knowledge gaps around the quantification and monitoring of direct and indirect impacts of heat exposure on maternal, newborn and child health (MNCH), by focusing on the following objectives:

- (1) **Indicators:** Using systematic reviews, data (re)analyses of heat impacts on maternal, newborn and child health outcomes, and data science predictive modelling on maternal and newborn health data from several countries including Greece, Italy, Sweden, Kenya and South Africa, we increase our understanding of the relationships between heat and maternal, newborn and child health outcomes and we inform the selection and tracking of global, European and national indicators.

- (2) **Early Warning System:** MotherHeat Alert, a smartphone app developed with support from TNO The Netherlands, delivers notifications and context-specific messages, co-designed locally. MotherHeat Alert is evaluated for its usability, acceptability and effectiveness, among 60 health workers and 600 mothers and infants in Sweden, South Africa and Zimbabwe.
- (3) **Adaptation and mitigation interventions:** We aim to identify cost-effective adaptation-mitigation interventions for health facilities. The design of adaptation interventions is informed by the assessment of environmental and thermal exposures in health facilities in Sweden, South Africa and Zimbabwe and by the health worker baseline assessments in both cold and hot seasons in the same countries. The design of mitigation interventions is based on carbon emission assessments conducted through the Aga Khan Development Network's carbon management tool in Kenya, South Africa and Zimbabwe and a resource allocation tool for carbon emission mitigation interventions in health facilities, CARBOMICA, developed by HIGH Horizons with support from Burnet Institute (Australia).
- (4) **Policy:** Throughout the project, HIGH Horizons engages relevant stakeholders, prioritising country partners, European Union, African and global policy makers at the intersection of climate and health.
- (5) **Biomarkers**⁴: Specific biomarkers are measured among pregnant women and their infants in a prospective mother-child birth cohort in Greece to better understand the role of heat exposure on adverse health outcomes. Urine-specific gravity is assessed as a heat-specific biomarker among participants in Zimbabwe and South Africa.

HIGH Horizons applies an interdisciplinary approach to achieve its five specific objectives by including biomedical and climate science, geospatial analysis, health systems thinking, health economics, and social and behavioural science. For this

⁴ This objective was added to the HIGH Horizons project in April 2023 when University of Thessaly (Greece) joined the consortium thanks to the Horizon Europe Hop On grant.

purpose, a wealth of data(sets) is reused and generated. Our data can be useful for researchers in the fields of climate change and heat; maternal, newborn and child health; implementation science; indicator development; early warning system (EWS) development; epidemiology, social sciences and health economics; and for policymakers working on impact of climate change on health.

The HIGH Horizons work packages are centred around baseline assessment (WP2), design (WP3), implementation (WP4) and evaluation (WP5), with project management (WP1) and communication & dissemination (WP6) being the overarching work packages.

2 Research data summary & description

Both data reuse and data generation support the HIGH Horizons studies.

Data reuse (DR). Existing de-identified data are reused and (re)analysed, mainly for assessing the impact of heat exposures on maternal, newborn and child health. Examples of secondary and de-identified data(sets) reused are

- Databases of environmental factors (e.g., temperature, humidity, air pollution): ERA5⁵;
- Maternal, newborn and child health outcomes at health facility, regional or country level, including amongst others
 - regional or nationwide birth registries (e.g. Greece, Italy, Sweden),
 - routine electronic medical records in health facilities (e.g. Kenya, South Africa), and

⁵ ERA5 is a state-of-the-art dataset that provides global gridded data every 1 hour at a 0.25x0.25° grid scale, providing data for regions where observations are sparse. ERA5 is the only product available open source that provides data for Mean Radiant Temperature and the thermal comfort index the Universal Thermal Climate Index as part of ERA5-HEAT. Mean Radiant Temperature is required to calculate Wet Bulb Globe Temperature, an international standard for heat stress. Both the Universal Thermal Climate Index and Wet Bulb Globe Temperature are thermal comfort indices of interest in HIGH Horizons.

- consolidated monthly survey data from the INDEPTH network and the Health and Demographic Surveillance System, from 29 sites from across 13 sub-Saharan African countries.

Data generation (DG). Data are generated in Greece, Kenya, South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe, being the countries where mitigation and adaptation interventions in health facilities are implemented and evaluated, or where findings from data analyses help to inform these interventions, such as the baseline health worker study to assess the wellbeing and productivity of health workers when exposed to heat or the application of the Aga Khan Development Network’s carbon management tool to measure the carbon emissions in selected health facilities. New data are also generated in these countries through testing and evaluating the EWS MotherHeat Alert, and in Greece through the mother-child cohort follow-up. Table 1 gives an overview of the data reuse and generation in each of the study countries of HIGH Horizons.

Table 1. Overview of data reuse and/or generation by country

Country	DATA REUSE	MAINLY DATA GENERATION			
	Data analysis for assessment of heat-health impacts (WP2)	EWS for pregnant women & health workers (WPs 3, 4 & 5)	Facility adaptation* (WPs 2, 3, 4, 5)	Facility mitigation** (WPs 2, 3, 4, 5)	Biomarker analysis (WP2)
Greece	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
Italy	Yes	No	No	No	No
Kenya	Yes	No	No	Yes	No
South Africa	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes [°]
Sweden	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
Zimbabwe	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes [°]

Notes:

* Facility Adaptation is to reduce heat/temperature in the facilities, e.g., fans, air conditioners.

** Facility Mitigation is to reduce greenhouse gases from facilities, e.g., solar panels, reducing emissions from waste.

[°] With the addition of the biomarker study in Greece, we also test 1-2 dehydration biomarkers in the cohorts recruited in South Africa and Zimbabwe to evaluate the EWS MotherHeat Alert.

For more details about which data we use or generate and how, we refer to the respective reports/deliverables in Table 2.

Table 2. HIGH Horizons deliverables with data management aspects

Number	Deliverable title*	Data reuse / generation
WP2: Assessment		
D2.1	Environmental-health databases 1 (10)	DR & DG
D2.2	Environmental-health databases 2 (August 2025)	DR & DG
D2.3	Heat-health analysis report from Greek, Italian, Swedish and African data 1 (11)	DR & DG
D2.4	Heat-health analysis report from Greek, Italian, Swedish and African data 2 (August 2025)	DR & DG
D2.6	Updated systematic review 1 (12 & 13)	DR
D2.7	Updated systematic review 2 (August 2025)	DR
D2.8	Environmental exposures in health facilities (14)	DR & DG
D2.9	User-friendly tool for heat-related risk assessment of the working environment in health facilities (August 2025)	
D2.10	Health workers impact baseline analysis (August 2025)	DR & DG
D2.11	Carbon emission assessment (15)	DR & DG
D2.12	Study initiation package (16)	DG
D2.13	Midterm recruitment report (17) ^o	DG
WP3: Design & selection		
D3.1	Expert Group established and operational (18)	DR
D3.2	Methods for selection of indicators (18)	DR
D3.3	Report on predictive heat warning thresholds (19)	DR
D3.4	MotherHeat Alert prototype: An early warning system app for pregnant and postpartum women, infants and young children, and health workers (20)[^]	DR & DG
D3.5	Report on photo voice sub-study, and the locally-adapted and optimised messaging (21)	DG
D3.6	Report on selection of alternative adaptation interventions ^{^^}	DG
D3.7	Tool for modelling of alternative mitigation interventions (22)	DR & DG
WP4: Implementation		
D4.1	Training on use of monitoring indicators (23) ^o	DR & DG
D4.2	Annual report on MNCH indicator application 1 (24) ^o	DR & DG
D4.3	Annual report on MNCH indicator application 2 (August 2025)	DR & DG
D4.8	Completion of adaptation intervention South Africa and Zimbabwe (25) ^o	DG
D4.9	Completion of mitigation intervention Kenya, Zimbabwe & South Africa (26) ^o	DG
WP5: Evaluation		
D5.2	Protocol for testing of the EWS among pregnant and postpartum women, and young children (27)	DG
D5.4	Protocol and ethics approval for health facility adaptation interventions (28) ^o	DG
D5.5	Evaluation of experiences and effectiveness of adaptation in health facilities (August 2025)	DG
D5.7	Protocol and ethics approval for mitigation interventions evaluation (29)	DG

Notes: * When the project deliverable is approved, we deposit it in the EU Open Research Repository in Zenodo, so that we have a persistent identifier (see also chapter 4.1). ^o Deliverables which have not yet been approved, but will be uploaded on Zenodo once approved. [^] An updated version of this report, including new name and logo of the app, is due August 2025. ^{^^} Not deposited in Zenodo because changes were made to the methodology to select adaptation interventions.

Tables 3 and 4 show the reused data and generated data, and their data management characteristics, including amongst others:

- data format (spreadsheet, recording,...)
- mode of data collection (observational, survey,...)
- file format
- data lifecycle stage (raw or processed data)
- availability of personal data (yes/no)
- data transfer/sharing agreement (yes/no).

In the last column of these tables, we refer to the connected project deliverable that describes the dataset and analysis results, and which are also listed in table 2.

When the dataset is final, we highlight the row to show that these details are complete, and where applicable we hyperlink to the persistent identifier of the dataset. Most of the datasets will be uploaded in a trusted repository when the results are published, and therefore most persistent identifiers are missing.

The overview with the HIGH Horizons datasets contains more characteristics than those shown in tables 3 and 4, including details about data controllers and data processors. These details are shared amongst the research projects of the European climate and health cluster but not made publicly accessible.

We estimate that HIGH Horizons will generate and reuse data with a size of at least 20TB⁶.

⁶ The dataset with environmental factors, with calculations of heat indices such as UTCI and WBGT, has a size of approximately 20 TB.

2.1 Reuse of secondary and de-identified data and other research outputs (DR)

Table 3. Data reuse by HIGH Horizons

Ref #	Data object/format	Data content	Mode of data collection	File format	Data lifecycle stage	Personal data	Direct identifier	Data size	Open sharing	Legal/ethical requirement	Deliverable
WP2 - Assessment of heat-health impacts and gaps in health facility adaptation and mitigation											
DR2.1	ERA5 reanalysis dataset with daily temperature, mean radiant temperature and thermal comfort	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	netcdf (.nc)	Raw, processed and published data	No	No	20TB	Yes	Not applicable	D2.3 & D2.4 (forthcoming)
DR2.2	Nation-wide birth register data for Greece, 1991-2021	Numerical & textual data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Processed data	Yes	No	312MB	No	Data transfer agreement between UTH and ELSTAT	D2.3 & D2.4
DR2.3	Database with time series of human thermal stress indices in Greece, aggregated at commune level	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Processed data	No	No	1.85GB	Yes	Not applicable	D2.3 & D2.4
DR2.4	Certificate of Delivery Care Registry for Lazio region, 2001-2019	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	SAS7BDAT	Processed data	Yes	No	700MB	No	Data use agreement for ASL Roma	D2.3 & D2.4
DR2.5	Swedish Population Registry, 2000-2022	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Processed data	Yes	No	1.26GB	No	Data sharing agreement between data provider and KI	D2.3 & D2.4
DR2.6	Database of MNCH outcomes in Aga Khan Hospital in Mombasa, 2017-2022	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Processed data	Yes	No	25KB	No	Data sharing agreement between AKHS Kenya and UGRAZ	D2.3 & D2.4
DR2.7	Health facility register from Soweto (South Africa), 2017-2022	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Processed and published data	Yes	No	37GB	No	Data sharing agreement between data provider and Wits RHI	D2.3 & D2.4
DR2.8	Consolidated HDSS data from 29 sub-Saharan African Sites, 1990-2018	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Processed and published data	No	No	1GB	Yes	Not applicable	D2.3 & D2.4

Ref #	Data object/format	Data content	Mode of data collection	File format	Data lifecycle stage	Personal data	Direct identifier	Data size	Open sharing	Legal/ethical requirement	Deliverable
DR2.9	National Health Birth Outcomes, Austria, 2002-2022	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Processed and published data	No	No	11MB	No	Data sharing agreement between UGRAZ & GöG	D2.3 & D2.4
DR2.10	Summary table of studies on association between high temperatures and MNCH outcomes & included in the systematic literature review	Numerical & textual data	Derived/compiled from other sources	.pdf	Published data	No	No	2MB	Yes	Not applicable	D2.6
DR2.11	Combined spreadsheet with indoor and outdoor temperatures at the health facilities in South Africa, Sweden and Zimbabwe	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv); DMY	Raw, processed and published data	No	No	10MB	Yes, upon publication	Not applicable	D2.8
DR2.12	Spreadsheet with climate and health terms, their definitions and sources	Textual data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv) & DOC (.doc)	Published data	No	No	100KB	Yes	Not applicable	Not applicable
DR2.13	Database with routine data about health services and human resources (baseline) in South Africa	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Raw, processed and published data	Yes	No	2MB	No	Ethics approval for Wits RHI	D2.10 (forthcoming)
DR2.14	Database with routine data about health services and human resources (baseline) in Zimbabwe	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Raw, processed and published data	Yes	No	2MB	No	Ethics approval for CeSHHAR	D2.10
DR2.15	Electronic Birth Notification Registry for Belgium, 2012-2022	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Processed and published data	Yes	Yes	155MB	No	Data processing agreement for Study Centre for Perinatal Epidemiology & Centre d'Épidémiologie Périnatale	D2.3 & D2.4
DR2.16	Perinatal Information System for Latin America and the Caribbean, 2008-2022	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Processed and published data	No	No	-	No	Not applicable	D2.3 & D2.4
DR2.17	ALERT project data, 2021-2023	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Processed and published data	No	No	10MB	No	Not applicable	D2.3 & D2.4

Ref #	Data object/format	Data content	Mode of data collection	File format	Data lifecycle stage	Personal data	Direct identifier	Data size	Open sharing	Legal/ethical requirement	Deliverable
WP3 - Design surveillance, Early Warning Systems, and health facility adaptive and mitigation actions											
DR3.1	Algorithms/scripts rewritten in Flutter from the original ClimApp software application	Not applicable	Not applicable	.dart and .JSON	Not applicable	No	No	16MB	No	Data processing agreement with TNO	D3.4
DR3.2	API to retrieve the local weather conditions from OpenWeatherMap for alerts in MotherHeat Alert	Numerical data	Compiled through GPS and API from OpenWeatherMap	.JSON, .XML, and .HTML	Published data	No	No	5MB	Yes	Not applicable	D3.4

2.2 Generation of primary data and other research outputs (DG)

Table 4. Data generation by HIGH Horizons

Ref #	Data object/format	Data content	Mode of data collection	File format	Data lifecycle stage	Personal data	Direct identifier	Data size	Open sharing	Legal & ethical requirement	Deliverable
WP2 - Assessment of heat-health impacts and gaps in health facility adaptation and mitigation											
DG2.1	Spreadsheet with indoor temperature and air humidity in selected health facilities in South Africa	Numerical data	Observational	HOBO (.hobo); CSV (.csv)	Raw data	No	No	9MB	Yes, upon publication	Not applicable	D2.8
DG2.2	Spreadsheet with indoor temperature and air humidity in selected health facilities in Sweden	Numerical data	Observational	HOBO (.hobo); CSV (.csv)	Raw data	No	No	4MB	Yes, upon publication	Not applicable	D2.8
DG2.3	Spreadsheet with indoor temperature and air humidity in selected health facilities in Zimbabwe	Numerical data	Observational	HOBO (.hobo); CSV (.csv)	Raw data	No	No	8MB	Yes, upon publication	Not applicable	D2.8
DG2.5	Spreadsheet with carbon emission measurements in health facilities in Kenya	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	XLS (.xls)	Raw and processed data	No	No	13.5MB	Yes, upon publication	Not applicable	D2.11
DG2.6	Spreadsheet with carbon emission measurements in health facilities in South Africa	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	XLS (.xls)	Raw and processed data	No	No	12.5GB	Yes, upon publication	Ethics approval for Wits RHI	D2.11

Ref #	Data object/format	Data content	Mode of data collection	File format	Data lifecycle stage	Personal data	Direct identifier	Data size	Open sharing	Legal & ethical requirement	Deliverable
DG2.7	Spreadsheet with carbon emission measurements in health facilities in Zimbabwe	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	XLS (.xls)	Raw and processed data	No	No	80MB	Yes, upon publication	Not applicable	D2.11
DG2.8	Spreadsheet with time-motion study results (baseline) in South Africa	Numerical & string data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No	16MB	Yes, upon publication	Ethics approval for Wits RHI	D2.10 (forthcoming)
DG2.9	Spreadsheet with time-motion study results (baseline) in Zimbabwe	Numerical data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No	16MB	Yes, upon publication	Ethics approval for CeSHHAR	D2.10
DG2.10	Spreadsheet & unstructured text with results of participant observation of the work environment and activities conducted at baseline in health facilities in South Africa	Numerical & textual data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	Yes	16MB	No	Ethics approval for Wits RHI	D2.10
DG2.11	Spreadsheet & unstructured text with results of participant observation of the work environment and activities conducted in health facilities (baseline) in Zimbabwe	Numerical & textual data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	Yes	6MB	No	Ethics approval for CeSHHAR	D2.10
DG2.12	Audio recordings of baseline in-depth interviews with healthcare workers in South Africa	Audio-visual data	Observational	MPEG4 (.m4a)	Raw data	Yes	Yes	1GB	No	Ethics approval for Wits RHI	D2.10)
DG2.13	Transcripts based on audio recordings of baseline in-depth interviews with healthcare workers in South Africa (DG2.12)	Textual data	Observational	.txt	Processed data	Yes	No	100MB	Yes, after embargo	Ethics approval for Wits RHI	D2.10
DG2.14	Audio recordings of in-depth interviews (baseline) in Zimbabwe	Textual & audio-visual data	Observational	MPEG4 (.m4a)	Raw data	Yes	Yes	5.17GB	No	Ethics approval for CeSHHAR	D2.10
DG2.15	Transcripts and analyses based on audio recordings of DG2.14	Textual & audio-visual data	Observational	NVP (.nvp); .txt	Processed data	Yes	No	700MB	No	Ethics approval for CeSHHAR	D2.10

Ref #	Data object/format	Data content	Mode of data collection	File format	Data lifecycle stage	Personal data	Direct identifier	Data size	Open sharing	Legal & ethical requirement	Deliverable
DG2.16	Dataset about wellbeing, psychological status, perceived heat stress and thermal comfort, and how the health workers feel, administered by the health workers themselves (baseline), in South Africa	Numerical & textual data	Survey	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	Yes	5MB	No	Ethics approval for Wits RHI	D2.10
DG2.17	Spreadsheet with results of urine samples (baseline) in South Africa	Numerical data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	Yes	26KB	No	Ethics approval for Wits RHI	D2.14 (forthcoming)
DG2.18	Spreadsheet with results of urine samples (baseline) in Zimbabwe	Numerical data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	Yes	26KB	No	Ethics approval for CeSHHAR	D2.14
DG2.19	Dataset about wellbeing, psychological status, perceived heat stress and thermal comfort, and how the health workers feel, administered by the health workers themselves (baseline), in Zimbabwe	Numerical & textual data	Survey	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	Yes	356KB	No	Ethics approval for CeSHHAR	D2.10
DG2.20	Dataset of FitBit observations in South Africa	Numerical data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	Yes	40MB	No	Ethics approval for Wits RHI	D2.10
DG2.21	Dataset of FitBit observations in Zimbabwe	Numerical data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	Yes	38MB	No	Ethics approval for CeSHHAR	D2.10
DG2.22	Dataset of core body sensors data/observations in South Africa	Numerical data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	Yes	35MB	No	Ethics approval for Wits RHI	D2.10
DG2.23	Dataset of core body sensors data/observations in Zimbabwe	Numerical data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	Yes	35MB	No	Ethics approval for CeSHHAR	D2.10
DG2.24	Algorithms/scripts of the heat-health data analyses	Numerical data	Simulation data	.R, .ipynb and .py	Processed data	No	No	33KB	Yes	Not applicable	D2.3 & D2.4
WP3 - Design surveillance, Early Warning Systems, and health facility adaptive and mitigation actions											
DG3.1	Images from the Photovoice sub-study in South Africa	Visual data	Observational	JPEG (.jpeg)	Raw data	Yes	Yes	137MB	Yes	Ethics approval for LSHTM & Wits RHI	D3.5

Ref #	Data object/format	Data content	Mode of data collection	File format	Data lifecycle stage	Personal data	Direct identifier	Data size	Open sharing	Legal & ethical requirement	Deliverable
DG3.2	Images from the Photovoice sub-study in Zimbabwe	Visual data	Observational	JPEG (.jpeg)	Raw data	No	No	544MB	Yes	Ethics approval for LSHTM & CeSHHAR	D3.5
DG 3.3	Audio recordings of Photovoice workshops with pregnant/postpartum women and FGDs with health workers in the development of messages in South Africa	Audio-visual data	Observational	MPEG4 (.m4a)	Raw data	Yes	No	1.5GB	No	Ethics approval for LSHTM & Wits RHI	D3.5
DG3.4	Transcripts based on audio recordings from messaging development in South Africa	Textual data	Observational	DOC (.doc)	Raw and processed data	No	No	100MB	No	Ethics approval for LSHTM & Wits RHI	D3.5
DG 3.5	Audio recordings of Photovoice workshops with pregnant/postpartum women and FGDs with health workers in the development of messages in Zimbabwe	Audio-visual data	Observational	MPEG4 (.m4a)	Raw data	Yes	No	163MB	No	Ethics approval for LSHTM & CeSHHAR	D3.5
DG3.6	Transcripts based on audio recordings from messaging development in Zimbabwe	Textual data	Observational	DOC (.doc)	Raw and processed data	No	No	54KB	No	Ethics approval for LSHTM & CeSHHAR	D3.5
DG3.7	Database with findings from transect walks in South Africa	Categorical & textual data	Observational	DOC (.doc)	Raw data	Yes	No	120MB	No	Ethics approval for LSHTM & Wits RHI	D3.5
DG3.8	Database with findings from transect walks in Zimbabwe	Categorical & textual data	Observational	DOC (.doc)	Raw data	Yes	No	119MB	No	Ethics approval for LSHTM & CeSHHAR	D3.5
DG3.9	Database with characteristics of the EWS users and their thermal exposure when using MotherHeat Alert in South Africa	Numerical & categorical data	Observational	CSV (.csv) or JSON	Raw data	Yes	Yes	5MB	No	Ethics approval for South Africa	D3.4 & D5.3 (forthcoming)
DG3.10	Database with characteristics of the EWS users and their thermal exposure when	Numerical & categorical data	Observational	CSV (.csv) or JSON	Raw data	Yes	Yes	5MB	No	Ethics approval for Sweden	D3.4 & D5.3

Ref #	Data object/format	Data content	Mode of data collection	File format	Data lifecycle stage	Personal data	Direct identifier	Data size	Open sharing	Legal & ethical requirement	Deliverable
	using MotherHeat Alert in Sweden										
DG3.11	Database with characteristics of the EWS users and their thermal exposure when using MotherHeat Alert in Zimbabwe	Numerical & categorical data	Observational	CSV (.csv) or JSON	Raw data	Yes	Yes	5MB	No	Ethics approval for Zimbabwe	D3.4 & D5.3
DG3.12	Database with research questions and answers, plus user details, collected through MotherHeat Alert Research Screen in South Africa	Categorical & textual data	Observational	CSV (.csv) or JSON	Raw data	Yes	Yes	5MB	No	Ethics approval for South Africa	D3.4 & D5.3
DG3.13	Database with research questions and answers, plus user details, collected through MotherHeat Alert Research Screen in Sweden	Categorical & textual data	Observational	CSV (.csv) or JSON	Raw data	Yes	Yes	5MB	No	Ethics approval for Sweden	D3.4 & D5.3
DG3.14	Database with research questions and answers, plus user details, collected through MotherHeat Alert Research Screen	Categorical & textual data	Observational	CSV (.csv) or JSON	Raw data	Yes	Yes	5MB	No	Ethics approval for Zimbabwe	D3.4 & D5.3
DG3.15	Algorithms/scripts of the EWS/MotherHeat Alert for pregnant women, postpartum women, infants and health workers in Zimbabwe	Numerical & textual data	Design thinking	Flutter code	App code	No	No	-	Yes, on GitHub once programming is done	IP agreement with TNO (subcontracted)	D3.4
DG3.16	Building performance modelling to guide the selection of building interventions in Mt Darwin	Numerical & categorical data	Simulation data	xls	Processed data	No	No	-	Yes, upon publication	Not applicable	D2.8
DG3.17	Scripts for CARBOMICA modelling	Numerical & textual data	Design thinking & data science	.py	Raw data	No	No	200KB	Yes	Not applicable	D3.4

2.3 Other research outputs to be collected, generated or reused in the project

Other research outputs of HIGH Horizons (apart from primary and secondary data) include data analysis scripts to assess the heat-health impacts, software developed for the smartphone application MotherHeat Alert, and the CARBOMICA resource allocation tool for mitigation interventions. The related algorithms, scripts and models are included in table 4 above.

As far as physical outputs are concerned: specimens such as whole blood, serum, urine from pregnant women, newborns, infants and fathers (Table 5), are collected in Greece and analysed with the purpose of examining the association of biomarkers related to heat exposure and MNCH outcomes. Urine samples of health workers and pregnant women in South Africa and Zimbabwe won't be collected, only the results of the dipstick test and refractometer.

Table 5. Specimens collected in the mother-child cohort study in Greece

Sample type	Mother	Father	Child*
Whole blood (whole blood, serum, plasma)	YES	YES	YES
Cord blood (whole blood, serum, plasma)	YES	N/A	N/A
Urine	YES	YES	YES
Saliva	YES	YES	YES
Nasopharyngeal swabs	YES	YES	YES
Vaginal swabs	YES	N/A	N/A
Rectal swabs	YES	-	YES
Faeces	YES	-	YES
Meconium	N/A	N/A	YES
Hair	YES	-	YES
Colostrum	YES	N/A	N/A
Breast milk	YES	N/A	N/A
Guthrie cards	N/A	N/A	YES
Placental/umbilical cord issue	YES	N/A	N/A
Genetic material	YES	YES	YES

Notes: *The term *child* refers here to newborns and infants up to one year of age. N/A : not applicable.

3 Ethical and legal issues

3.1 Open access restrictions

Because personal and sensitive data are collected in the HIGH Horizons studies, ethical clearances and legal arrangements are essential before conducting the studies and these have an impact on (open) data sharing as well.

The ethics approvals obtained, and data transfer agreements signed within the HIGH Horizons project are listed below.

Datasets with personal data. Since various HIGH Horizons-generated data are health-related, personal and sensitive, we cannot provide full open access to all our datasets. As such, some datasets are not entirely openly available and conditions are attached to access the data (= restricted access). Where possible, we take actions to limit the restrictions, i.e., to have our datasets "as open as possible, as closed as needed", by pseudonymisation or anonymisation of personal data where possible and by agreeing on a limited embargo period (i.e., an embargo period of 5 years after finalising the project). We will grant access to 'summary statistics' following analysis of data as appropriate.

Actions to limit the restricted access include the following:

- All individual-level data on women, children, and health workers, using observations, checklists, interview guides, photos, recordings and questionnaires, are anonymised at the point of data collection. An identification number specific to the study is used to distinguish each participant and to each facility.
- Data from focus group discussions and key informant interviews are anonymised (if possible) or pseudonymised. Audio files of focus group discussions or interviews are destroyed; their (de-identified) transcripts are available.
- Data from the cohorts testing the early warning system in South Africa, Sweden and Zimbabwe and the mother-child cohort recruited for the biomarker study in Greece cannot be anonymised as we need to keep the link between personal and

health information during the cohort period. However, we will pseudonymise these data to secure their privacy.

The final decision about how openly accessible the HIGH Horizons datasets will be, will be taken by the Steering Committee at the end of the project based on the sensitivity of the data, the importance of sharing our data and findings for secondary analyses as well as the quality.

Datasets with personal data are securely stored by HIGH Horizons partners on their local servers, and only anonymised data(sets) are shared internally between HIGH Horizons partners, as well as externally in trusted repositories.

The research teams in Kenya, Sweden, South Africa and Zimbabwe remain owner of the samples and data they collect. The provider and the processor will be involved in deciding how to restrict future use of the data in collaboration with the Steering Committee.

Non-personal data (e.g. environmental or temperature data) are made openly available where relevant.

De-identified data. HIGH Horizons does not collect direct identifiers such as name, home address. However, we will have indirect identifiers such as date of birth.

GDPR register. Minimal personal data from HIGH Horizons partners and stakeholders are stored securely on the HIGH Horizons SharePoint folder, and are not accessible by external partners. We do not keep a GDPR register for the HIGH Horizons project.

Data transfer agreements. Several data transfer agreements between HIGH Horizons partners have been established for internal data sharing and analysis.

3.2 Ethics approvals

Our approach for ethics applications is:

- Prepare a 'mother protocol' (by the lead partner of the study), including procedures to guarantee confidentiality, such as informed consent forms, alignment with the GDPR rules, secure data storage and management of personal data;
- Seek ethical clearance for the 'mother protocol' from the Ethics Committee or Institutional Review Board of the lead partner;
- Modify and align the mother protocol to the requirements of the Ethics Committee or Institutional Review Board in each of the implementing countries;
- Seek ethical clearance for the 'country protocol' from each of the Ethics Committees.

We have received ethical clearance for all required study protocols (see table 6).

When the mother protocol is an approved HIGH Horizons project deliverable, we have deposited it in Zenodo (see protocols #2, 4, and 5b). For protocol #3, we have prepared a generic study protocol (30) on how HIGH Horizons analyses and assesses the population-level heat-health impacts in the countries for which we have a database⁷. This study protocol can be used by others to analyse country data they own. Data scripts and data analysis plan will be shared publicly once the results are published.

⁷ Apart from the country datasets available to HIGH Horizons partners in Greece, Sweden, Kenya and South Africa, a subcontractor from our Swedish partner KI, ASL Roma, has access to a regional dataset in Italy. Its data access and usage are regulated by regional and national laws to which ASL Roma Department of Epidemiology of the Lazio Region Health Service complies.

Table 6. Overview of HIGH Horizons protocols and their status

Protocol #	Topic	Lead partner	Greece	Kenya	South Africa	Sweden	Zimbabwe
Protocol #1	#1a. Protocol for pre-intervention assessment of health workers' wellbeing	LSHTM; APPROVED	Not applicable	Not applicable	APPROVED	APPROVED	APPROVED
	#1b. Protocol for post-intervention assessment of health workers' wellbeing	LSHTM; this study will be included in protocol #6	Not applicable	Not applicable	This study is included in protocol #6	This study is included in protocol #6	This study is included in protocol #6
Protocol #2	Protocol for pre-post study evaluation of mitigation interventions (29)	CeSHHAR; Protocol but no application	Not applicable	Not applicable	APPROVED	Not applicable (because no mitigation interventions)	Not applicable because no human subjects research
Protocol #3	Protocol for access to and reuse of birth registry and MNCH data	UGRAZ; APPROVED	APPROVED	Data sharing agreement with UGRAZ	APPROVED	Not applicable	Not applicable
Protocol #4	Protocol for biomarker study (16)	UTH; APPROVED	APPROVED	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable
Protocol #5	#5a. Protocol for co-design of locally-appropriate messages	LSHTM; APPROVED	Not applicable	Not applicable	APPROVED	APPROVED	APPROVED
	#5b. Protocol for design and pilot testing of EWS & evaluation (27)	ULUND; Protocol but no application	Not applicable	Not applicable	APPROVED	APPROVED	APPROVED
Protocol #6	Protocol for co-design of adaptation interventions	LSHTM; Protocol but no application	Not applicable	Not applicable	Protocol but no ethics application	Not applicable	Protocol but no ethics application

3.3 Valorisation of research

Within HIGH Horizons we do not have data or research materials subject to confidentiality due to valorisation potential. We do not foresee any patent applications.

3.4 Third-party agreements

So far, we do not have any data or research materials affected by third-party agreements.

3.5 Intellectual property

The predictive models based on heat stress indices and human heat balance models, algorithms, and source codes of the MotherHeat Alert are already openly accessible through GitHub. All coding modifications made during the HIGH Horizons project are similarly made available as they are produced. The app is developed in the Open-Source Platform Cordova (Apache Cordova) and built for specific smartphone platforms (e.g., Android). The app is hosted by HIGH Horizons partner ULUND and their subcontractor TNO, and the data are saved by TNO and shared with ULUND through a data sharing agreement. The ClimApp consortium currently owns the app. For teaching and research ClimApp, it is free, but for commercial use, the ClimApp consortium must agree.

4 Metadata and documentation

4.1 Findable and accessible data

Repositories. For datasets and other research materials HIGH Horizons mainly uses two **trusted repositories**, Zenodo and GitHub:

- HIGH Horizons has created its own community as part of the Zenodo [Open repository for EU-funded research](#), which is set up specifically for research outputs from Horizon Europe: [Search HIGH Horizons \(zenodo.org\)](#); our approved project deliverables are deposited in Zenodo in these two communities;
- On GitHub we created our own [HIGH Horizons repository](#), but many researchers also share their datasets or software in their own public repositories.

Metadata. We follow the repository guidelines for the **metadata**, including description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo; Horizon Europe and UKRI funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset or research material, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant.

Upon submission in the data repository, we provide search keywords to optimise our data and research materials for reuse. Where possible the same keywords are used in the publications. We also use Zenodo's harvest module to record metadata in the Zenodo community collection.

Persistent identifiers. HIGH Horizons uses **persistent identifiers** for

- authors: *ORCID ID*
 - We encourage all HIGH Horizons researchers to register with ORCID
- organisations: *ROR ID*
 - Except for Wits Health consortium (and its health research divisions, Wits RHI and Wits Planetary Health Research) and Aga Khan Health services Kenya, all HIGH Horizons consortium partners have a ROR
- grant: *ID grant number*
 - In the metadata we refer to Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101057843 and UKRI Innovate UK reference number 10038478
 - We also acknowledge funders by adding "HIGH Horizons has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Framework Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101057843. Project partner LSHTM is funded by UKRI Innovate UK reference number 10038478" to publications or project deliverables
- publications: *DOI* (e.g., peer-reviewed journal article) or *ISBN* (e.g., WHO publications)
 - For most of our research outputs and publications the editor or repository

provides the DOI

- Zenodo also registers DOIs for deposited records and research outputs
- datasets: *DOI*
 - The dataset of the heat-health glossary is deposited in [GitHub](#) and [Zenodo](#) (31) and more datasets are deposited once cleaned and final
 - We also consider sharing anonymised processed data on Zenodo in the future
- software: *DOI*
 - The codes of [ClimApp](#) and the changes made for the personalised early warning system for pregnant women and health workers, MotherHeat Alert, is shared openly on GitHub by the developers and once the MotherHeat Alert is final we plan to deposit the software in Zenodo to have a DOI for the software
 - The scripts and codes for [CARBOMICA](#), the resource optimisation tool for carbon emission mitigation interventions, are also deposited in GitHub by the developers, and we also consider to deposit them in Zenodo once final.

In Zenodo metadata are publicly accessible and licensed under public domain, so no authorisation is ever necessary to retrieve it. Data will remain available and findable for 20 years. Metadata will remain available after 20 years. For accessing the data in Zenodo the user may need to be registered and require login to the user's account, but this also depends on the level of access chosen by HIGH Horizons (i.e. closed, open, or embargoed access).⁸

⁸ [Zenodo](#) (access and reuse)

4.2 Interoperable data

The HIGH Horizons data is mainly processed by the researchers in REDCap⁹, ODK¹⁰, Wombat¹¹, NVivo, MaxQDA, Word and Excel, but data sharing will be in non-proprietary formats (.pdf, .txt, .csv), which are interoperable. The linked metadata make the data partly machine readable. Where possible the formats that are preferred by the repositories (i.e. Zenodo, GitHub) are used.

Standard vocabulary is used, such as country codes and ISO format of date-time. We will use the standard vocabulary used in clinical trials¹² and correct applicable clinical ontologies. In addition, we document all variables throughout the study.

Because HIGH Horizons is situated at the intersection between climate and health sciences, the terminology used by the different disciplines has been inventoried in a heat-health glossary (31). No other project-specific ontologies or vocabularies are used.

5 Data storage & security

Data storage. The handling of the overall data management, the HIGH Horizons' SharePoint folders and files, the UGent shared network drive "shares" and repositories on behalf of HIGH Horizons, as well as general data management issues related to the project, are the responsibility of the project coordinator. The storage of confidential and personal information from questionnaires, informed consent forms and urine and

⁹ REDCap is a secure web application for building and managing online surveys and databases. The software is not open source but is installed on a local web server, e.g. at the University of Thessaly where it is used for the biomarker study, or at Wits RHI, ULUND and CeSHHAR for collecting data during the EWS implementation and evaluation.

¹⁰ LSHTM uses the ODK platform: [LSHTM ODK Servers - LSHTM Global Health Analytics](#). ODK is an open source electronic data capture tool maintained by a collaborative global community. The LSHTM Global Health Analytics group has set up an ODK service to help scientific researchers use ODK in their projects. This service is available on a pay-what-you-can basis to anyone working at LSHTM, or collaborating with LSHTM researchers on research that can benefit global health. The use of ODK has to be acknowledged in publications: "Electronic data solutions were provided by LSHTM Global Health Analytics (odk.lshtm.ac.uk)."

¹¹ WOMBAT, Work Observation Method by Activity Timing, is a computerised tool to collect multiple dimensions of clinical work patterns (who, what, when and why) as well as comprehensive contextual information (patients and colleagues) and interrupted tasks.

¹² <https://prsinfo.clinicaltrials.gov/definitions.html>

blood sample data are managed locally by our partners in Greece, South Africa, Sweden and Zimbabwe.

Data security. Data security is of major importance in the HIGH Horizons project. The protection of personal data is ensured through procedures and appropriate technologies, including:

- Through all steps in data gathering, data entry, data cleaning, and analysis, only HIGH Horizons team members have access to the data. The respective data managers will regularly evaluate that people have access only to the information that they strictly need to have access to.
- The Ghent University SharePoint is used for secure storage at the consortium level. This instance is set up 'on-premise,' meaning that the data are stored within Ghent University. This ensures that the data are protected in case a device is lost or stolen and guarantees better protection in terms of privacy. SharePoint also provides a backup mechanism for versioning.
- Each HIGH Horizons partner stores the data collected on its institutional network, on a secure server protected by two-level authentication.
- Data storage on local devices is avoided at all times. If storing a copy of the data on local machines is inevitable, then the data will be password-protected and only include de-identified data.
- Screens are locked when researchers leave their desks.
- Data are not sent by email but transferred safely using encryption or secure tools like Filesender (and not WeTransfer, Dropbox or Box).
- When working in a non-digital format: physical access to confidential data will be controlled; for example, field notes or a box of confidential interviews (transcripts, field notes) or completed informed consent forms will not be left unattended behind locked doors.

- When the retention period of confidential data has expired, and there are no further obligations or reasons to keep them, this information will be destroyed safely. This could mean shredding paper before it is disposed of for physical documents. As for digital data, special erasing software will be used.
- The study results may be published for scientific purposes, but anonymity will be protected at all times, and no results will be linked to specific individuals.

6 Data preservation

As project coordinator, Ghent University encourages all HIGH Horizons partners to preserve the relevant research data for a minimum of 5 years¹³. Specimens such as whole blood, serum, and urine from pregnant women and cord blood collected by UTH in Greece are stored 30 years after collection, in accordance with the traceability obligations set out in Art.36 of Greek Presidential Decree 26/2008, which transcribes Directive 2004/23/EC into Greek Law.

Data and research materials will be safely stored for long term preservation and curation, because the security standards of the trusted repositories apply. The HIGH Horizons datasets and other research outputs that need to be preserved after the project will be listed in the final DMP at the closure of HIGH Horizons.

7 Data sharing and reuse

All the datasets that HIGH Horizons deposits in online repositories with the purpose of being shared and reused are listed (see tables 3 and 4). Data and research materials deposited in the trusted repositories will include README files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.

¹³ See UGent's RDM policy framework (4): [Preserving data — Ghent University \(ugent.be\)](https://www.ugent.be/en/research-operations/rdm/policies/preserving-data)

The HIGH Horizons Steering Committee will decide on granting access to the data collected and produced after consulting the relevant owners and processors. If granted access, licenses will be given depending on the purpose of the secondary analysis. Embargo periods may apply.

After project closure decisions about granting access to the open data and research outputs will be taken by the respective partner organisations.

8 Costs and resources

HIGH Horizons uses repositories free of charge for storing and accessing data. If costs related to data management occur during the HIGH Horizons project, these will be covered by the Horizon Europe grant, but this has not been the case as of date (August 2025). At this stage we do not expect costs for long-term storage and archiving and therefore it is expected that no financial resources are required after project closure.

9 References

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